

THE SYNONYMY OF IDIOMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article talked about the phraseology of linguistics and the history of its formation, scientists who contributed to its development. In addition, the article described the importance of expressions and their impact on our speech. Also, examples of common phrases in Uzbek and English were taken, and their meanings were explained, as well as the similarity of meaning between phrases and phrases was shown with vivid examples.

Key words: phraseologism, phrase, synonymy, own and figurative meaning.

The professor of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan Azim Hajiyev wrote: "Phraseology is a branch of linguistics that studies phraseological units, meaning "phrasal - phrase, expression, logos - science, education, teaching" in Greek" ¹. Phraseology works with idioms and phrases in a language, and this part of linguistics formed in Russian linguistics in the 40s of the 20th century. After that a myriad of searches have been conducted so as to study phraseology deeply and develop it. Russian scientists, such as A. A. Shaxmatov, A. A. Potebniya, made a great contribution to the improvement of this linguistic branch. A. V. Kunin had a great role in the development of English phraseology. The study of phraseology in Uzbek linguistics began in the 50s of the last century. Until now, many scientists have studied various areas of phraseologism in depth, and special dictionaries have been developed that express idioms and their meanings. The services of linguists Sh.Rakhmatullayev, B.Yuldoshev, and A.Mamatov are incomparable.

We utilize idioms to make our speech rich, beautiful and to increase its poetic licence. On the ground that they assist to describe and imagine with ease. If a person uses more idioms and phrases in an appropriate and meaningful way, it means that they have wide horizon and rich vocabulary. Lexical, semantic and other aspects of phraseologism have been studied during last years.

In Uzbek language, idioms usually have synonyms with words and other idioms, that is to say, an idiom can be synonym with another idiom. Even some idioms have several synonymous idioms at the same time. For example, **og'zining tanobi qochmoq** – to be extremely happy. Synonyms: og'zi qulog'iga yetmoq; boshi ko'kka yetmoq; terisiga sig'may ketmoq; qo'yi mingga yetmoq.² So we can use other four idioms meaning the same with the idiom og'zining tanobi qochmoq instead. And this shows that our speech is much more expressive. Despite this, there are some idioms in Uzbek linguistics that both the usage and the synonymy-antonymy of which are limited. This means such kind of idioms do not have

¹ Hojiyev A. Lingvistik terminlarning izohli lug'ati. T., 1985, 105-bet.

² Sh. Rahmatullayevning «O'zbek tilining izohli frazeologik lug'ati»

any synonyms, we can explain their meanings only with simple words. For instance, **yuzidan o'ta olmaslik** - to consider someone's opinion and desire when doing something³.

Below, we will learn examples of some phrases in Uzbek language with their own and figurative meaning and synonymy with other phrases:

1. **Do'ppisini osmonga otmoq** - a) in its own meaning "to throw one's hat (duppi) to the sky". b) in a figurative meaning "be extremely happy". Synonym: boshi ko'kka yetmoq.

Example: Yig'layotgan bolani ovutish maqsadida do'ppisini osmonga otdi (He threw his hat (duppi) in order to comfort the crying child) - own meaning.

Bu xushxabarni eshitib, do'ppisini osmonga otdi (He got extremely happy hearing the good news) - figurative meaning.

2. **Ipidan ignasigacha** - in every detail, down to the last detail. Synonyms: miridan-sirigacha, qilidan quyrug'igacha.

Example: U bo'lib o'tgan noxush voqea haqida ipidan ignasigacha so'rab surishtirdi (He inquired about the unpleasant incident that happened).

3. **Tarvuzi qo'ltig'idan tushmoq** - when a person is disappointed because the result of a work is not in the state he expected. Synonym: hafsalasi pir bo'lmoq⁴.

Example: Odamlar tarvuzi qo'ltig'idan tushib, qishloqqa qaytishdi. (M.Ismoiliy)⁵ (People came back to the village in a bad mood).

In English like Uzbek language there are own and figurative meanings of idioms, their synonymy with other phrases. For instance, the idiom, fork smth out (on smth) - to spend a lot of money on something, usually money you don't want to spend, can be synonymous with pay smth out. Now, here we will see some examples like this:

1. **There's nothing to it** - it's very easy. This idiom has an alternative in Uzbek language "xamirdan qil sug'urganday". Synonyms: easy-peasy; a piece of cake.

Example: - Is it a difficult game? - No, there's nothing to it.

2. **Fly by** - if a period of time flies by, it passes very quickly. It means "ko'z ochib yumuncha" in Uzbek. Synonym: flash by.

Example: Fine, Luisa was shy at first but gradually she came out of her shell and we talked about our friends, travelling and the like. In fact, the time just flew by.

3. **To give anything to sb or smth** - used to say that you would like to have or to do something very much. In Uzbek, we say this "borini bermoq, baxshida qilmoq, har narsaga tayyor bo'lmoq".

Synonym: to give sb right arm to sb or to do smth.

Example: I'd give anything to see the Taj Mahal.

Janice would give her right arm for a house like that⁷.

So idioms that are used to give our speech beauty and increase its expressiveness have their own and figurative meaning in both English and Uzbek languages. Some can have synonyms with another idiom. By utilizing idioms, phrases, proverbs and such kind of different colorful linguistic expressions, not only we can show our wide vocabulary, but also we can describe our intended view in an easier and more attractive way.

³ Sh. Rahmatullayevning «O'zbek tilining izohli frazeologik lug'ati»

⁴ A. Anorbekova, Sh. Mrzayeva "Hozirgi O'zbek adabiy tili" T., 2011.

⁵ Z. Toshboyeva "Matnda shaxs ruhiy holatini ifodalovchi vositalar".

⁶ Ruth Gairns and Stuart Redman "Idioms and Phrasal Verbs" Oxford Word skills Advanced, 2011.

⁷ Dictionary.cambridge.org

References:

- 1.A. Anorbekova, Sh. Mirzayeva “Hozirgi O‘zbek adabiy tili” (“Current Uzbek literary language”)T., 2011.
- 2.<https://Dictionary.cambridge.org>
- 3.Haydarov Anvar Askarovich (BuxDU, (BukhsU)), Saidova Zulfizar Xudoyberdiyevna (BuxDU, (BukhsU)) “Ruhij jarayonlar va shaxsiyat xususiyatlari konseptual zonasi frazeologizmlarining struktur grammatik tahlili” (“Structural Grammatical Analysis of Phraseologisms of the Conceptual Zone of Mental Processes and Personality Traits”).
- 4.Hojiyev A. “Lingvistik terminlarning izohli lug‘ati” (“Explanatory dictionary of linguistic terms”). T., 1985.
- 5.Ruth Gairns and Stuart Redman “Idioms and Phrasal Verbs” Oxford Word skills Advanced, 2011.
- 6.<https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Frazeologiya>
- 7.Zebiniso Toshboyeva “Matnda shaxs ruhiy holatini ifodalovchi vositalar” (“Means of expressing a person's mental state in the text”).
- 8.Sh. Rahmatullayevning “O‘zbek tilining izohli frazeologik lug‘ati” (“An explanatory phraseological dictionary of the Uzbek language”).

